

Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedure Template

Subtitle which is a description of subject

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Introduction

The introduction section describes the need for and scope of the procedures documented here. Include a general overview that foreshadows the main sections in this SOP. Which specific procedures will be covered, and which are not covered? Be very concise and precise. Use active language to describe the steps undertaken to complete the procedure.

The motivation for developing this SOP is <insert>. The primary audience for this SOP is <insert>. This SOP assumes basic working knowledge of <insert>.

Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**. Resources such as templates, spreadsheets, GitHub repositories, and other materials that are used to implement the procedures are listed in **Table 2**.

Roles and Responsibilities

Describe each person with a role in this standard operating procedure. Note that you are identifying only the role and the responsibilities associated with the role for the procedures described in this SOP. Responsibilities that are outside the scope of this procedure should not be included. Only include roles that are actually involved in the procedures outlined in this SOP.

Table 1. Sample roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Project Manager	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu
Lead Organ Contact (LOC)	various	various
Medical Illustrator	Heidi Schlehlein	hschleh@iu.edu

Relevant Resources

If the procedures documented in this SOP require access to a number of resources like templates, spreadsheets, SOPs, or GitHub repositories, consider including an optional Relevant Resources section with a table, see **Table 2**, that provides links to these resources in one location.

Table 2. Resources used in these procedures.

Name	Purpose	Location
Mailing list	Communication with working group members	https://groups.google.com/a/hubmapconsortium.org/g/ASCT-B
Experts survey	Qualtrics survey for joining the HRA Open Working Group	https://iu.co1.qualtrics.com/jfe/preview/SV_bpaBhIr8XfdiNRH?Q_CHL=preview&Q_SurveyVersionID=current
Mapping Virtual Millitomes to Reference Organs	Standard Operating Procedure for using 3D millitome mesh-based models to scale tissue registration into the Human Reference Atlas	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7901004
HRA-AMAP GitHub Repository	Enables automated projection of tissue blocks from a source organ to a new reference organ.	https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-amap

Procedures

Break procedures into separate sections if they are long. Provide the sequence of tasks and subtasks for the given procedure.

Section heading

The procedure can be broken into sections to make comprehension easier. Use a descriptive section heading to help readers navigate the SOP.

Use bulleted lists to visually show task hierarchy:

- Task
 - Subtask 1
 - Subtask 2
- Task
- Task

Subsection heading

- Do use figures or screen shots when helpful to illustrate tasks.

- Note that the SOP should not become the documentation for a user interface, but remains focused on the required steps for completing a specific procedure.
- If there are existing documents, video demos, or talks that explain the procedures, please add links to these in the introduction or, where appropriate, in the main body of the SOP.
- Before you submit an SOP for review, please test it by asking two members of the target audience to follow the procedures. This helps surface gaps in the instructions.

Figure 1. Sample figure with caption

References and Resources

Reference materials can include normative documents, instructions, and standards as well as research papers, websites, videos, and other SOPs. These are cited from the main text using Zotero. Included here are examples of how to cite references in different formats, including a published paper (Bueckle et al. 2026), a preprint in BioArxiv (Hu et al. 2025), online links or websites such as the HRA Organ Gallery (Bueckle and Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2024), videos (Bueckle and Phatnani 2024), and Human Reference Atlas SOPs published on Zenodo (“SOP: Using 3D Reference Objects | Zenodo,” n.d.).

Bueckle, Andreas and Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center. 2024. “HRA Organ Gallery.” <https://humanatlas.io/hra-organ-gallery>.

Bueckle, Andreas, Bruce W. Herr, Lu Chen, et al. 2026. “Cell Type Populations for 3D Anatomical Structures of the Human Reference Atlas.” *Scientific Data*, ahead of print, March 19. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-026-06642-4>.

Bueckle, Andreas, and Hemali Phatnani. 2024. "2024-11-05 Senescence VR Demo." YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wy0BCOFWClk&ab_channel=CyberinfrastructureforNetworkScienceCenter%28CNS%29.

Hu, Joyce, Beverly Peng, Ajith V. Pankajam, et al. 2025. "Benchmarking Single Cell Transcriptome Matching Methods for Incremental Growth of Reference Atlases." Preprint, bioRxiv, April 16. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.04.10.648034>.

"SOP: Using 3D Reference Objects | Zenodo." n.d. Accessed October 27, 2022. <https://zenodo.org/record/5944025#.Y1qxHuTMImA>.

Glossary

Define important terms and abbreviations used in this SOP in this section. When available, use definitions from the [SOP Glossary](#), which includes the most current definitions used throughout the Human Reference Atlas. They should align with standard terminologies used within your field. New or revised definitions must be reviewed before they are added to the master glossary.

procedure: A step by step description of how to accomplish a set of related tasks. Procedures usually describe a specific way of undertaking a process in a detailed way.

role: One's position on a team.

standard operating procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style (e.g., plain English).

task: A piece of work, usually undertaken as part of a larger procedure.

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